

Mild and efficient synthesis of chalcone via Claisen-Schmidt condensation reaction using dicationic benzimidazolium based ionic liquid

Prashant Narayan Muskawar, Sainath Babaji Aher and Pundlik Rambhau Bhagat*

Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drprbhagat111@gmail.com

Abstract : Dicationic benzimidazolium based ionic liquid (IL) plays a dual role as catalyst and solvent which offers a potential candidature for conventional homogenous catalysts and solvent for Claisen-Schmidt condensation being carried out between substituted benzaldehyde and acetophenone to produce chalcones. This IL has shown good catalytic activity towards the chalcones synthesis and chalcones can simply be separated from mixtures by simple decantation of dissolved chalcones. Catalyst can be efficiently recovered and reused without any significant loss of catalytic activity. The optimized reaction conditions were investigated for various substituents like electron withdrawing or donating group on benzaldehyde.

Keywords : Chalcones, Claisen-Schmidt condensation, dicationic ionic liquids.

Introduction

Chalcones have been synthesized by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of acetophenone and benzaldehyde derivatives comprising of a three carbon α,β -unsaturated carbonyl system. They can be found majorly in eatable plants and exhibits diverse range of pharmacological properties. Chalcones plays a major role as anti-infectives and antiparasitic in plants. They have indicated extensive curative role in humans like anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antibacterial, and many more reviewed in detail¹.

Ionic liquids (ILs) possess various properties like solvent, catalysis and many more. ILs are having good catalyst properties, which has been reviewed in detail^{2,3}. The reaction of interest i.e. chalcones synthesis using ILs as catalyst has been studied in detail⁴⁻⁶. Conventionally, chalcones are being synthesised in aq. NaOH. While greener approach has been done using ILs for chalcones synthesis catalyzed by some SO_3H -functionalized ionic liquids like *N,N,N*-trimethyl-*N*-propane-sulfonic acid ammonium hydrogen sulfate [TMPSA][HSO_4]⁵, *N*-propane sulfonic acid pyridinium hydrogen sulfate [PyPSA][HSO_4]⁵ and many more. Catalyst separated by decantation technique which can be reused few times without perceptibly loosing the catalytic activity.

So here we have carried out eco-friendly solvent free method for chalcones synthesis using dicationic benzimidazolium based ionic liquid as a catalyst.

Results and discussion

The Claisen-Schmidt condensation catalyzed by [DCBim]BF₄ :

The [DCBim]BF₄ having Lewis acid character which activate carbonyl group of aldehyde i.e. increases in the electrophilicity of carbonyl group. Cation part of IL increases the nucleophilic nature of ketone. Hence IL play a key role in the CS condensation. Benzaldehyde (1) and acetophenone (2) have been reacted to produce *trans*-chalcone (3) (Scheme 2) with 10% [DCBim]BF₄. Benzaldehyde derivatives varied so as to achieve various substituted chalcones. Experimental data has been presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental data for reaction conversion

Entry	Compd. no.	R-CHO	Reaction time (h)	% Yield
1	CS-1	-H	3	88
2	CS-2	2-OCH ₃	3.2	79
3	CS-3	4-OCH ₃	3.2	82
4	CS-4	3-Cl	3.0	83
5	CS-5	4-Cl	2.5	85
6	CS-6	4-NO ₂	2.8	91

IL has been successfully used as a catalyst for chalcones formation from various derivatives of benzaldehyde and acetophenone. *ortho*-Anisaldehyde (entry 2) gives less yield

than *para*-anisaldehyde (entry 3), which is due to electron donating nature and steric hindrance produced by -OCH₃ group. *para* Substituted chloro benzaldehyde (entry 5) gives better yield compare to *meta*-substituted benzaldehyde (entry 5). The effect of electron withdrawing group is observed with *para*-nitro benzaldehyde (entry 6) as it shown excellent yield with acetophenone.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

All solvents and reagents purchased commercially and used without further purification unless otherwise stated. Benzimidazole purchased from Loba, sodium hydride from SDFCL, tetrahydrofuran from Avra, sodium tetrafluoroborate from Sigma-Aldrich and ethane-1,2-diyl bis(2-chloroacetate) synthesized in our laboratory from monochloroacetic acid and ethane diol. Also aromatic aldehydes and acetophenone had been purchased SDFCL.

Preparation of IL :

We have synthesised the ionic liquid as reported method⁷ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of (DCBIM)BF₄.

Preparation of 3,3'-(2,2'-(ethane-1,2-diylbis(oxo))bis(2-oxoethane-2,1-diyl))bis(1-propylbenzimidazolium) tetrafluoroborate (DCBIM)(BF₄) :

Initially benzimidazole treated with 1-bromoethane in THF using NaH (60%) at 60 °C for 48 h. In next step, *N*-ethyl benzimidazole reacted with ethane-1,2-diyl bis(2-chloroacetate) in toluene at 90 °C for 48 h leads to the formation of dicationic benzimidazolium based IL having chloride anion. This further stirred with aq. NaBF₄ leads to replacement of Cl by BF₄. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, TMS) : δ 1.56 (3H, t), 4.46 (3H, s), 4.63 (2H, q), 5.59 (2H, s), 7.75 (2H, m), 8.03 (1H, d), 8.15 (1H, d), 9.73 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, TMS) : δ

14.2, 42.3, 47.3, 63.5, 113.8, 113.9, 126.7, 126.9, 130.5, 131.5, 142.9, 166.6; ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, TMS) : δ 148.26. MS-ES⁺, Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₈N₄O₄²⁺ 436, Found (M²⁺/2) + 1 = 219.

Reaction procedure (Scheme 2) :

Benzaldehyde derivative, acetophenone and IL (1 : 1 : 0.1 mole ratio) has been taken in three naked round bottom flask provided with condenser. Reaction mixture was stirred at 100 °C in oil bath under N₂ atmosphere with automated temperature control system. Reaction progress monitored by TLC with mobile phase as *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate 1 : 1. Upon completion of reaction confirmed by TLC, reaction flask removed and cooled to RT. Ethyl acetate added where IL get precipitated, filtered and washed with ethyl acetate (3 × 20 ml) for recovery of IL. Ethyl acetate extract had been washed with water (3 × 20 ml) and finally with brine. Organic layer dried over Na₂SO₄ and evaporated to collect yellowish solid, recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 54–56 °C.

Synthesis of 3-phenyl-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (1) :

Benzaldehyde treated with acetophenone leads to for-

Scheme 2. The CS condensation of benzaldehyde and acetophenone.

mation of 1. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 3.86 (3H, s), 6.93 (2H, d), 7.39 (1H, s), 7.43 (1H, s), 7.49 (2H, t), 7.57 (3H, q), 7.77 (1H, s), 7.81 (1H, s), 8.0 (2H, d); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 55.48, 76.84, 77.16, 77.48, 114.51, 119.86, 127.69, 128.50, 128.65, 130.32, 132.64, 138.59, 144.79, 161.78, 190.66.

Synthesis of 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (2) :

o-Anisaldehyde reacted with acetophenone leads to formation of **2**. m.p. 58–60 °C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 7.40 (2H, d), 7.51 (3H, t), 7.58 (3H, q), 7.74 (1H, s), 7.78 (1H, s), 8.02 (2H, d); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 76.84, 77.16, 77.48, 122.60, 128.63, 128.81, 129.38, 129.73, 133.07, 133.51, 136.57, 138.16, 143.44, 190.38.

Synthesis of 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (3) :

p-Anisaldehyde reacted with acetophenone leads to formation of **3**. m.p. 77–78 °C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 3.91 (3H, s), 6.95 (1H, d), 6.99 (1H, t), 7.36 (1H, t), 7.50 (1H, t), 7.6 (3H, q), 7.63 (3H, d), 8.01 (2H, d), 8.10 (1H, s), 8.14 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 55.67, 76.84, 77.16, 77.48, 111.36, 120.87, 123.02, 124.06, 128.66, 129.37, 131.88, 132.66, 138.66, 140.55, 158.94, 191.28.

Synthesis of 3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (4) :

3-Chlorobenzaldehyde reacted with acetophenone leads to formation of **4**. m.p. 69–71 °C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 3.83 (3H, s), 6.89 (2H, d), 7.45 (1H, s), 7.37 (1H, s), 7.49 (2H, t), 7.62 (3H, q), 7.74 (1H, s), 7.89 (1H, s), 8.0 (2H, d); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 55.57, 76.74, 77.20, 77.48, 114.45, 119.77, 127.75, 128.0, 128.65, 130.39, 132.69, 139.59, 144.87, 161.88, 190.44.

Synthesis of 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (5) :

4-Chlorobenzaldehyde reacted with acetophenone leads to formation of **5**. m.p. 110–112 °C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 3.83 (3H, s), 6.89 (2H, d), 7.43 (1H, s), 7.38 (1H, s), 7.48 (2H, t), 7.64 (3H, q), 7.76 (1H, s), 7.89 (1H, s), 8.04 (2H, d); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 56.67, 76.78, 77.25, 77.43, 114.49, 119.72, 127.79, 128.1, 128.61, 130.33, 132.65, 139.55, 144.82, 161.89, 190.42.

Synthesis of 3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (6) :

4-Nitrobenzaldehyde reacted with acetophenone leads to formation of **6**. m.p. 156–158 °C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 3.81 (3H, s), 6.89 (2H, d), 7.41 (1H, s), 7.35 (1H, s), 7.43 (2H, t), 7.63 (3H, q), 7.72 (1H, s), 7.83 (1H, s), 8.06 (2H, d); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) : δ 56.62, 76.74, 77.22, 77.45, 114.47, 119.74, 127.78, 128.15, 128.63, 130.35, 132.67, 139.56, 144.84, 161.87, 190.44.

Conclusion

The benzimidazole based dicationic ionic liquid has been synthesised and used as an efficient catalyst for synthesis of chalcones via the Claisen-Schmidt condensation between aldehyde and ketones. IL is recovered by precipitation from ethyl acetate after finishing reaction for easy recovery. IL has shown good catalytic role as observed from yield of the reaction. Yield has been affected by the electron withdrawing or electron donating nature the substituent present on benzaldehyde. Electron withdrawing group enhances the reaction rate while electron donating groups reduces the reaction rate considerably.

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